

EDUCATION AND CREDIBILITY OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RURAL COMMUNITIES OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study undertook a comprehensive control mechanism of students in public secondary schools in the rural communities of Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria. In traditional African society settings, the processes of educating young adults had taken place before the invasion of Africa by colonial masters who on arrival condemned and destroyed our education system. Akwa Ibom's traditional education society has a well-structured and specific traditional system which involves the acquisition of knowledge and skills transferred from one generation to another. This work assessed the level of credibility of public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State in this millennium as compare to what was before now. Various theoretical perspectives on education were considered. The public secondary schools within the senatorial districts were analysed. Findings showed that there is cultinization of young people in public secondary schools which has led loss of educational credibility. The researcher recommended that all public schools in rural communities must be provided with perimeter fences and gatehouses to effectively control entry and exit of students and non-student visitors.

KEYWORDS: Education, Public Secondary Schools Development, Rural Communities Akwa Ibom State

INTRODUCTION

In traditional African society, education was regarded as social responsibility, job creation, and political participation, spiritual and moral values. Children and young adolescent were engaged in participatory education through ceremonies, rituals, initiations, recitations and demonstrations. Parson (1970) argued that the central institution of the pattern maintenance subsystem is the family. It is the unit which transmits the first and most influential experience of the society. Education is the process through which an individual is admitted into any society by being taught what is worthwhile, in that, the individual might play his part well and contribute positively to the society he lives in. Adedayo (1998) noted that pre-primary and primary Education are the edifice which should be strongly built. Durkheim (1947) argued that education is an important instrument through which society perpetuates itself. It is by respecting school rules in general that he developed the habit of self-control and restrain himself, noting that it is the first initiation into the austerity of duty which

marks the beginning of serious life.

African children and adolescents were involved in practical farming, fishing, weaving, knitting, carving, cooking, etc. While recreational subjects were wrestling, drumming, dancing, racing and acrobatic display. Plants, animals, local geography, poetry, riddle and reasoning and local history were intellectual training. In preindustrial societies, such as those of medieval Europe specialized education institutions slowly developed along with the specialized roles of teachers and they provided formal education for small minority of the population such as future members of the clergy and the sons of the wealthy, Lords and kings. It was during industrialization era that formal education for the masses began, Moumouni (1968).

In Akwa Ibom State and in Nigeria, formal education is divided into two groups: the public and the private schools. The private school includes those of individual and missionary schools. The public schools for the masses while the private and missionary schools are for the well to do who can pay for their children and wards.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The main tribes of Akwa Ibom States are; Anaang, Ibeno, Ibibio, Itu Mmon Uso, Obolo and Oron. The people of the Akwa Ibom State are known for their stride in Education. In the year 2008 the Government of Akwa Ibom State declared free and compulsory Education from primary to secondary schools. The Government paid for both internal and external examinations at all level from primary one to West African Examinations Councils Examination (WAEC) including the Senior Secondary Two Mug Examinations, to ensure that children of all classes of citizens in the State's community participate equally. Habison and Myeric (1971) quoted in Nya (2024) stated that education is the key that unlocks modernization, while Emile Durkheim (1974) argued that, education is an instrument through which society perpetuates itself.

At 12 to 14 years the child enters into his/her early adolescent hood where the child will be between JSS3 and SSS1. Here a child from a loose family loose from the gripe of his/her parents and freely swims in the net of his peer(s). The parents cannot control him and the teacher is afraid of him and what his cult group can do. In the morning they leave home for school but they are not found at school. In the public school, students can enter and leave the school compound at will because of its porousness. The public schools in the rural community have gate and a gate house at the front view but halfway around the compound, it is empty. In the year 2023, the Akwa Ibom State government approved the recruitment of security for public schools without providing perimeter fencing around the school compound to keep not only the teachers safe from non-students but also to keep safe the properties she had spent so much to boost the free and compulsory education in the state. There is a State Parents Teachers Association (P.T.A) forum where all the PTA chairman, principals of public schools and the Hon Commissioner of Education meet quarterly. It is very hard for this forum to manically address the ugly situation in our public secondary schools, because out of every One Hundred and Fifty (150) SSS3 students or so that wrote the WAEC every year in our public schools less than ten (10) diligently write the examination for by our very existence, some of us have proved to be the destroyers of our need and our aspirations which lie open to our very selves, and our parents who help to support our failures and self-disappointment with their laissez-faire attitude on their whimsy children.

The founding fathers considered formal education as an investment in democracy because it would create a literate, active and informed public, thus preventing the privileged few from having a monopoly on marketable skills to becoming inundated especially in urban areas by many ethnic groups migrated from rural areas with circumspect mind. Sociologically speaking, the social construction of identity today is knowing the construction of identity that “your life is your project.” For pertinacity is personal aspiration fixed in the child from the beginning of which the child will attained his status as a successful adult leading an exhilarating life.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Emile Durkheim (1974) Opined that, education is the instrument through which the society perpetuates itself, that it is one of the most powerful human institution that shapes and influences man, society and environment. Public schools or state run schools be it primary or secondary are controlled by democratic authority and administration. Although the individual or private schools have their own elected school board also known as Parents Teachers Association (PTA). State and federal Government play a crucial role in the overall direction of the schooling, in public school therefore PTA have legitimate say in how the school should be run.

Public school is not supposed to be responsive simply to the needs of those who use the school's services. It is intended to serve within public purpose as determined by the government. Proponent of public schools believed that the objective of early school to be not so much but to refine intellectual culture as the regulation of feelings and dispositions, the extirpation of vicious propensities, the pre-occupation of the wildness of the young heart with seeds of lovely and virtuous characters by the habitual practice of cleanliness, delicacy refinement, good temper, gentleness, kindness, justice and truth Katz (1975:13). In most if not all of the public schools in the rural communities in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria, secret cult and cultism had driven Katz's theory into hell, making the young adults to live above the control of their parent both inside and outside their home treating education with levity vacuity and vapidty.

Private and Missionary Schools

Private and missionary schools have a great deal and more room to manoeuvre because of being shaped by a diverse group of constituents, private school is the responsibility of its proprietor and a small group of consumers, the parents who are paying school fees for their children and wards to attend the school. They may remove their children to another school if they feel that the quality of teaching is not sufficient. In Akwa Ibom State, private schools have a good and unassailable well secure environment with boarding facilities. External influence, indiscipline and all forms of misconduct which are inimical to society are taken care of and are controlled to the barest minimum.

A good school has an orderly climate, disciplinary policies that students and administrators believe to be fair and effective, high enrolment in academic courses regular assignment of homework and lower incidence of student absenteeism class cutting and other misbehaviours Ravitch (1982:10). These qualities are absent in all Public Secondary Schools where abrasive behaviour assisted by notoriously, is the order of the day without circumscription principles.

PHILOSOPHY OF EDUCATION

Ekanem *et al* (1981) noted that, Education is a set of processes that aims at getting some other things outside of itself which are aims and objectives.

Aim:

The aims of education in Nigeria are:

- (a) A free and democratic society.
- (b) A just and egalitarian society
- (c) A united, strong and self-reliant nation
- (d) A great and dynamic economy
- (e) A land of bright and opportunities for all citizens.

Objectives:

The objectives of Nigeria education are:

- i. The inculcation of national consciousness and national unity.
- ii. The inculcation of the right type of values and attitude and the survival of the individual and the Nigerian society
- iii. The training of the mind in the understanding of the world around
- iv. The acquisition of appropriate skill, abilities and competencies both mental and physical as equipment.

FUNCTIONALISTS PERSPECTIVE OF EDUCATION

Durkheim (1961) argued that society can only survive if there exists among its members a sufficient degree of homogeneity, that education perpetuates and reinforces this homogeneity by fixing the child from the beginning the essential similarities, cooperation, social solidarity, if not, the society itself would be impossible. A vital task for all societies is welding a mass of individual into the creation of social solidarity, which involves commitment to the society, a feeling that the social unit is more important than the individual so that there will be a sense of belonging.

To become attached to the society, there must be a feeling in him. Something that is real and alive, powerful and important which dominates him and to which he also owes the best part to himself, if he must survived. The functionalists maintained that education and in particular the teaching of history provides link between individual and his society. If the history of their society is brought alive to children, they will come to see that, they are part of something larger than themselves. To this they will develop a sense of commitment to the social group and the society.

In primary socialization within the family, the school takes over as the focal socializing agency for the school acts as a bridge between the family and society preparing children for their adult role, Parson (1961). Most children and students in public schools in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria do not know how Nigeria come to be, who is an Anaang or Ibibio man, how did he come be on his present location on the Planet Earth.

EDUCATION AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT

Woods (2002) argue that transmission of knowledge is the basic purpose of education. Education originally was the family responsibility but industrialization changed that dramatically. Education has a bearing on the economic well-being of our community and the

nation at large. Durkheim (1947) posted that education is an important instrument through which the society perpetuates itself. Education is the powerful instrument that shapes and influences man, society and the environment. Ekanem *et al* (2003:11) argue that education enables man to acquire appropriate skills, abilities and competencies both mental and physical equipment for the individual to live and contribute to the development of society.

POSTMODERN PERSPECTIVES ON EDUCATION

Usher *et al* (1914) opined that education promised to liberates the whole of humanity from ignorance and backwardness. It will help to spread the rationale on scientific beliefs that would free people from the grips of tradition and superstition. Individuals always had the potential to think for themselves and to make rational decisions but they were prevented from doing so in pre-modern society by the influence of superstitious belief and tradition. Usher and Edwards (1994) argued that the task of education under modernity was one of bringing out and helping to realized these potentials so that the subjects are fully autonomous and capable of exercising their individuality and intentionally vague. Education is the key to developed individuals and in doing so making social progress possible.

EDUCATION, TRAINING AND GENDER DEVELOPMENT

Informal and formal education is for public and social development. It improves the individual quality of life and offers him/her access to employment, income and political power. Nya (2024) argued that the girl child's education is however a priority because it is the key to gender equity justice and poverty reduction it improves skills and technical knowledge acquisition, improved nutrition, reproductive health and general socio-economic development by encouraging social participation across groups. With education, the girl child in her adulthood could easily gain employment in a formal labour force therefore not only contributing to her family income but also to the cross national product.

GIRL CHILD EDUCATION AND POLITICAL PARTICIPATION

When women achieve an equal share of political power, many things besides politics will change profoundly. Breaking the barriers that constrain the development of individual talent and restrict the range of human resources available to meet society's need will take place, Henry Alapiki (2010) in Nya (2024). In Akwa Ibom State, female education has gotten to the high level of enrollment across the state (Peters, Bassey and Usoro, 2020).

CREDIBILITY OF EDUCATION IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS

The first known formal education was established in Badary Nigeria by Mr. and Mrs. De Craft named "Nursery of the Infant Church" on 26th May 1843, Fafunwa (2004) from thence up to 1960s, women education was consider not beneficiary to her parent but only to her husband home. The girl child from their childhood was well groomed in kitchen routines, how she will be a good wife and the best of the mother among mothers, to respect her husband and her husband people but the boy child play around until when he is able to accompanied his father to hunting but he was not trained on how he will become a good husband, home management skills and the best of the father among fathers. He may grow to become a drunkard, snuffing and drug addicting at a very tender age to his grandfatherhood.

After the Nigerian civil war in 1970 women and girls in the South-South and in South East geopolitical became valuable. Parents started sending their girl child to formal education

training, today in public schools both in urban and in rural communities women comprise more than 65% of the student population and are found in the school compound during teaching and learning hours. Women And Development (WAD) and Women in Development (WID) organizations have ways and mean to enlighten women folks in their respective worship centers, village squares and meeting halls both in urban centers and in the rural communities campaigning for women emancipation.

More than 80%of boys from public secondary schools especially in the rural communities of Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria are not in schools, their learning activities if at all end in SS1. They constitute nuisance to the community. The boys in tertiary institutions are groomed from Private and Missionary schools in both urban and rural communities. There must be a reorientation for our attitudinal value. Durkheim (1961) argued that it is by respecting the school rules that the child learns to respect rules in general, that he develops the habit of self-control and restraint himself, noting that it is the first initiation into the austerity of duty which marks the beginning of serious life. To the prospects that leaned on adroitly and nous grow up to be successful and respectful.

CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL EXPLORATION

Functionalism and Postmodernism theories were chosen to explain the functions and gains of public education Emile Durkheim, Talcott Parson and Kingsley Davis among others are the major proponents of functionalism theory. While Robin Usher and Richard Edwards are the major proponents of the Postmodernism theory.

FUNCTIONALISM

Functionalists argued that after primary socialization within the family, the school take over as the focal socializing agency. School act as a bridge between the family and the society as a whole prepare children for their adult roles. Society can survive only if there exist among its member a sufficient degree of homogeneity. Education perpetuates itself and reinforces this homogeneity by fixing in the child from the beginning the essential similarities that collective life demands. Within the family the child's status is ascribed, it is fixed by birth. However in advanced industrial society, status in adult life is largely achieved, for example, individuals achieve their occupational status. Thus the child must move from particularistic standard and ascribed status of the family to the universalistic standard and achieve the standard of an adult in society. The school prepare young people for transition, Durkheim (1961).

POSTMODERNISM

Postmodernists maintained that education promised to liberate the whole of humanity from ignorance and backwardness. According to the premise of modernity, education will help to spread the rationale and scientific belief that would free people from the grip of tradition and superstition. Individual had the potentials to think for themselves and to make rational decision but they were prevented from doing this in pre-modern societies by the influence of superstition and tradition (Lyotard (1984)

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out in rural areas of Akwa Ibom State Nigeria. Akwa Ibom State was created on the 23rd of September 1987. Akwa Ibom State has a common boundary

with Abia State on the north, on the East by Cross River State, on the West by River State and on the South she is bounded by the mother Atlantic Ocean. Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Economy Planning and Development estimated a population of 7.2 Million for the State.

RESULTS

The State has Thirty One (31) Local Government Areas Twenty Six (26) State Constituencies, Ten (10) Federal Constituencies and Three (3) Senatorial Districts. The Public Secondary School of Akwa Ibom State before 31st January 2024, are;

Abak L.G.A	-	10	Public secondary schools
Eastern Obolo	-	3	Public secondary schools
Eket	-	8	Public secondary schools
Esit Eket	-	5	Public secondary schools
Essien Udim	-	9	Public secondary schools
Etim Ekpo	-	8	Public secondary schools
Etinan	-	11	Public secondary schools
Ibena	-	1	Public secondary school
Ibiono Ibom	-	10	Public secondary schools
Ika	-	4	Public secondary schools
Ikono	-	11	Public secondary schools
Ikot Abasi	-	4	Public secondary schools
Ikot Ekpene	-	7	Public secondary schools
INI	-	7	Public secondary schools
Itu	-	8	Public secondary schools
Mbo	-	3	Public secondary schools
Mkpat Enin	-	16	Public secondary schools
Nsit Atai	-	6	Public secondary schools
Nsit Ibom	-	7	Public secondary schools
Nsit Ubium	-	12	Public secondary schools
Obot Akara	-	5	Public secondary schools
Okobo	-	8	Public secondary schools
ONNA	-	8	Public secondary schools
Oron	-	3	Public secondary schools
Oruk Anam	-	14	Public secondary schools
Udung Uko	-	1	Public secondary school
Ukanafon	-	5	Public secondary schools
Uruan	-	9	Public secondary schools
Urue Offiong/Oruko	-	4	Public secondary schools
Uyo	-	14	Public secondary schools

Legislators, Ministers, Governors, Commissioners, Captain of Industries and who is who from Akwa Ibom State and Cross River State were the product of these schools but what happened at the turn of the third millennium is what nobody can explain. Cultism and cultinization of young adults became more pronounced in Public Secondary Schools than ever before in the history of this great state and Nigeria abnegating the future their Parents hope for.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

To remedy the ugly situation in the public secondary schools in our rural communities in Akwa Ibom State and in Nigeria, Government need to reintroduce reward and punishment principles in order to stamp out indiscipline in the secondary schools. Reorientation Principals and Teachers on the capacities and skills for effective control to guides behaviours and attitudes of students are indispensable.

Cultism must be totally brought to an end in all post primary schools be it in the urban area or rural community. Earnestly, teachers know who is who in their respective schools. Secondary schools were established to produce feature individuals and responsible personalities but not to produce reprehensible adults who kill the rosy life of rural communities. They lead outrageous lives that encourage responsible individuals to urban migrations.

Cohen and Lazerson (1972:47) argued that education is seen as work or the preparation for work. Schools were pictured as factories and the educators as industrial managers and students as raw materials to be inducted into the process. The ideology of school management was recast in the mould of the business corporation and the character of education was shaped by the image of industrial production.

The following are made for proper decision as regards to public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State and other rural communities in Nigeria to reconstitute morals, mores and values for proper formations, training, controlling and building of a progressive future in the young adolescents.

1. All public schools in rural communities must be provided with perimeter fences and gatehouses to effectively control entry and exit of students and non-student visitors.
2. History and Geography should be included among the compulsory subjects in secondary schools curriculum.
3. Every local Government Area should have a science and technical schools in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria.
4. A Scholastic Aptitude Test (SAT) should be reintroduced as a requirement for admission in to Nigerian Universities.

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